

TABLE 1 - DETAILS OF EXTRACTION METHODS

Parameter	Base				
	Pyridine	α -Picoline	β -Picoline	γ -Picoline	2,4,6-Collidine
pH	2-8	2-9	8-9	2-9	3-4
λ_{max} (nm)	345	370	485	365	360
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.95×10^4	1.75×10^4	1.85×10^4	3.70×10^4	1.09×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.05	0.018

Results and Discussion

The platinum complexes absorb maximum at 345–360 nm. The reagent blanks show insignificant absorbances in the aforesaid wavelength region. The systems show steady absorbances for at least 24 h. Maximum absorbances were found to be achieved when the extractions were carried out at pH 2–8, 2–9, 8–9, 2–9 and 3–4 for pyridine, α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine, respectively. Chloroform extracts obtained in the second consecutive operations in the respective pH range virtually showed no absorbance. This indicate a complete and quantitative extraction of platinum.

The optimum reagent concentrations were 2 ml of 0.05 M aqueous potassium iodide along with 0.5 ml of pyridine/ α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine to extract 100–500 μg of platinum. In all cases, Beer's law was found to be valid over the concentration range 5–50 ppm of Pt. The Ringbom's optimum concentration range for the measurement was found to be from 8–50 ppm of Pt^{IV} . The molar absorptivities of the complexes (on the basis of Pt content) and the respective Sandell's sensitivities were calculated as shown in Table 1.

Platinum(IV) was determined in presence of other diverse ions. In fact all the bases, i.e. pyridine, α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine showed similar behaviour towards the extraction of platinum. An ion was considered to interfere if the recovery of platinum(IV) differed by more than $\pm 3\%$ from the actual amount taken.

For the determination of 392 μg of Pt^{IV} (117.6 μg for collidine) a 25-fold excess of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{VI} , U^{VI} , Pb^{II} , Mn^{II} , V^V , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Cr^{III} , La^{III} , Be^{II} and Al^{III} did not interfere. A 10-fold excess of Cd^{II} , Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and a 5-fold excess of Rh^{III} were tolerable. A 5-fold excess of Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} could be kept in the aqueous phase with ammonium hydrogenfluoride and citrate, respectively. Hg^{II} and Pd^{II} interfered. Among the anions tested, the followings (50-fold excess) did not interfere: oxalate, borate, phosphate, tartrate, citrate, fluoride, bromide, phthalate, acetate. Lower concentration of EDTA is permissible. However, thiocyanate, thiosulphate and ascorbate interfered seriously.

2,4,6-Collidine was found to be most sensitive among the pyridine bases used. With this reagent the precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of platinum following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations containing 117.6 μg of Pt^{IV} gives a value of 115.5 μg , which varies between 114.52 to 116.44 at 95% confidence limit. The standard deviation is 0.92 μg .

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Electrochromatography of Metal Ions on Cerium(IV) Antimonate Papers. Quantitative Separation of Palladium(II) from Several Cations†

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IN continuation of our earlier studies on other antimonates¹⁻³, we have chosen cerium(IV) antimonate papers in the present work as this substance has been found to exhibit good ion-exchange properties in column operations⁴. Simple aqueous acids, mixtures of mineral acids and their ammonium salts and buffer mixtures of weak organic acids and the corresponding ammonium salts have been chosen as the background electrolyte solutions in these studies. On the basis of migration of metal ions under the combined influence of electric field and ion-exchange, a large number of separations of metal ions have been

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achieved. A quantitative separation of Pd^{2+} (2–10 μg) has also been developed from binary mixtures as well as from synthetic mixtures containing commonly interfering metals.

Experimental

Electrophoretic studies were performed on Whatman No. 1 paper strips (46.4×2 cm). A horizontal type electrophoresis apparatus run on an electronically regulated power supply unit (Systemics) was used. Spectrophotometric studies were performed on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-70 instrument.

Pure laboratory reagent grade chemicals and solvents (B.D.H., S.M., E. Merck, and Hopkin and Williams) were used.

Preparation of ion-exchange papers: Cerium(IV) antimonate papers were prepared by dipping the paper strips first in a 0.025 M antimony pentachloride (in 4 M HCl), dried for 15 min at room temperature and then again dipped in 0.025 M ceric ammonium sulphate. The excess reagent was allowed to drain off and the strips were left to dry over a filter paper sheet. The dried impregnated strips were washed twice with conductivity water in order to remove excess reagents and finally dried at room temperature.

Test solution and detection reagent: The test solutions were generally 0.1 M metal chloride or nitrate and were prepared as described earlier¹. Standard spot-test reagents were used for detection⁶. For quantitative work, a stock solution of Pd (10 mg ml^{-1} Pd) was prepared by dissolving PdCl_2 in dilute HCl.

Background electrolyte solutions: The following eleven aqueous and mixed background electrolyte solutions were used: (i) 0.1 M HCl, (ii) 0.01 M HCl, (iii) 0.001 M HCl, (iv) 0.1 M HCl + 0.1 M NH_4Cl (1 : 1), (v) 0.1 M HNO_3 + 0.1 M NH_4NO_3 (1 : 1), (vi) 0.1 M HCOOH + 0.1 M HCOONH_4 (1 : 1), (vii) 0.1 M CH_3COOH + 0.1 M $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (1 : 1), (viii) 0.1 M lactic acid + 0.1 M ammonium lactate (1 : 1), (ix) 0.1 M oxalic acid + 0.1 M ammonium oxalate (1 : 1), (x) 0.1 M tartaric acid + 0.1 M ammonium tartrate (1 : 1) and (xi) 0.1 M citric acid + 0.1 M ammonium citrate (1 : 1).

Procedure: The earlier method¹ was followed for qualitative studies of electrophoretic migration. For quantitative separation of palladium, 0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M HCl + 0.1 M NH_4Cl (1 : 1) were used as the electrolytes and current was passed for 4 h under a potential difference of 150 V. After electrochromatography, the strips were taken out and partially dried. The spot area was cut into pieces and Pd was eluted with 10% HCl (2 \times 20 ml) in cold. After the elution was complete, the strips were washed with distilled water (20 ml). The solution was then evaporated to small volume (2–3

ml) and the paper strips were oxidised with a mixture of HClO_4 – HNO_3 – H_2SO_4 in the ratio of 3 : 1 : 4. The solution was then evaporated to dryness and the residue was dissolved in a little distilled water. Palladium was determined in this solution by *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline method⁶ against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The electrophoretic migration distances (in cm) of 32 metal ions in all the background electrolyte solutions on plain as well as cerium(IV) antimonate paper were measured. On the basis of differences in migration distances and the direction of movement of cations several important and analytically difficult binary and ternary separations have been possible.

The electrochromatographic behaviour of metal ions on cerium(IV) antimonate papers in the background electrolytes used reveals interesting results. In the first three electrolytes, i.e. HCl systems, the value of M_4 (mobility of cations on plain papers – mobility of cations on impregnated papers) is found to increase with pH for most of the metals ions. However, Hg^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Pd^{2+} , Se^{2+} and Pt^{2+} show the reversal of behaviour and M_4 values decrease for these cations with the increase of pH. The increase of M_4 with pH indicates higher exchange at pH 3 and above. This is probably due to the fact that at pH 3 and above, number of H^+ ions is increased in solution due to the increased ionisation of the acid under these conditions. This causes higher exchange at pH 3 and above and consequently, the electrophoretic migration on cerium(IV) antimonate papers is reduced which results in the increased value of M_4 . The reversal behaviour observed in case of Hg^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Pd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Se^{2+} and Pt^{2+} may be due to the high selectivity of the exchanger cerium(IV) antimonate for these cations at high pH (pH 3 or above). The electrophoretic mobilities of cations in the electrolytes no. (iv) and (v) (which are mixture of mineral acids and their ammonium salts) are generally higher than the corresponding values in simple acids. It may be due to the high conductivity of these electrolytic solutions and the current is actually found to increase when electrophoresis is done in these background electrolyte solutions.

Background electrolytes no. (vi) to (xi) are all buffer solutions obtained by mixing weak organic acids with the corresponding ammonium salts. They indicate the effect of variation of ionisation constant of the acid on the electrophoretic mobility of metal ions on cerium antimonate papers under similar experimental conditions of voltage and time. The average mobilities of all the bivalent, trivalent and tetravalent metal ions used in these studies are found to decrease with the increase in ionisation constants of acids employed in preparing buffers. This decrease in mobility with ionisation constants is probably due to the increase in the

number of available H^+ ions competing with the metal ions in the exchange process.

The utility of cerium(IV) antimonate papers in electrochromatography is demonstrated by achieving several important and analytically difficult ternary and binary separations. On the basis of qualitative separation achieved, the quantitative separation of Pd^{2+} from several metal ions in simple aqueous electrolytes like 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M HCl+0.1 M NH_4Cl (1 : 1) is possible in only 3 h under a potential of 150 V. Apart from binary separations, Pd^{2+} (2–10 μg) was also quantitatively separated from different synthetic mixtures. In all, five synthetic mixtures were prepared by taking 5 μg each of the following cations: Bi^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Au^{3+} , Se^{4+} and Mo^{6+} along with Pd^{2+} . The amount of Pd^{2+} varied from 2–10 μg in these synthetic samples.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Disodium Ethylene-1,2-bisdithiocarbamate by Extraction of its Molybdenum Complex into Isobutyl Methyl Ketone

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DITHIOCARBAMATE have many uses, they are widely used as pesticides, especially as their metal complexes, and are applied in the rubber industry as vulcanisation accelerators and anti-oxidants. Most of the analytical methods in general use, are based on the Clarke method¹.

Dithiocarbamate pesticide residues, however, have been analysed²⁻⁴ by determining the released carbon disulphide spectrophotometrically, but these are time-consuming processes. It is considered of interest to determine dithiocarbamate (nabam) by a simple, direct and rapid spectrophotometric method.

We present here a more sensitive and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of nabam after extracting its molybdenum complex into isobutyl methyl ketone.

Experimental

A Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer was used for recording absorption measurements. Nabam was crystallised from a solution (Wilson Laboratories, Bombay). Ether was added to precipitate the dithiocarbamate, which was filtered off, recrystallised twice by dissolving in ethanol and precipitating with ether; the product was a hexahydrate. Purity was checked by elemental analysis and m.p (82°) and found to be the same as given in the literature. A 0.1% solution of nabam was prepared in distilled water and standardised¹ and further diluted as desired with distilled water. A 2% (w/v) sodium molybdate solution was prepared in distilled water. Stock solutions of other elements were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the elements to give the required composition.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 500 μg nabam in a beaker was added 2M H_2SO_4 (1.5–2.0 ml) and 2% sodium molybdate solution (2.0 ml). The final volume was made to 5 ml with distilled water. The solution was boiled for 5–7 min, then cooled and the final volume was again made to 5 ml with distilled water. The aqueous solution was transferred to a separatory funnel and shaken with isobutyl methyl ketone (5 ml) for 1 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the organic phase was transferred into a dry tube containing anhydrous calcium chloride. Extract with another 5 ml of methyl isobutyl ketone from the aqueous phase gave negligible absorbance indicating extraction of the complex in the first step itself. The absorbance of the dried solution (first step) was taken and measured at 670 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of nabam–Mo complex in MIBK was recorded against the reagent blank. The complex absorbed strongly at 670 nm. The absorbance of the extract increased with the addition of upto 1.5–2.0 ml of 2 M H_2SO_4 but decreased with further addition. The absorbance of the extract remained constant for 2.0–3.0 ml of 2% sodium molybdate solution and the